

Measurement Items

Construct	Code	Measurement Item
Relative Advantage (RA)	RA1	Using AI-based cybersecurity tools is time-saving for me.
	RA2	Using AI-based cybersecurity tools is highly efficient for me.
	RA3	Compared to traditional cybersecurity methods, AI-based tools are very useful for me.
	RA4	AI-based cybersecurity tools would have a positive impact on my work.
	RA5	I can immediately see the benefits of implementing AI-based cybersecurity tools.
Compatibility (CB)	CB1	AI-based cybersecurity tools fit well with the way I prefer to work.
	CB2	AI-based cybersecurity tools align with my work style.
	CB3	AI-based cybersecurity tools are compatible with the systems I currently use.
	CB4	AI-based cybersecurity tools fit well within my professional responsibilities.
	CB5	AI-based cybersecurity tools align with my preferred way of performing tasks.
Complexity (CX)	CX1	Learning to use AI-based cybersecurity tools is challenging for me.
	CX2	It is difficult to get AI-based cybersecurity tools to do what I want them to do.
	CX3	My interactions with AI-based cybersecurity tools are not always clear or straightforward.
	CX4	Using AI-based cybersecurity tools is not convenient for me.
	CX5	Overall, AI-based cybersecurity tools are complicated to use.
Triability (TR)	TR1	I had the opportunity to try AI-based cybersecurity tools before deciding whether to adopt them.
	TR2	I was able to try AI-based cybersecurity tools correctly before deciding whether to use them.
	TR3	I was allowed enough time to explore AI-based cybersecurity tools and understand what they can do.
	TR4	I usually learn about new cybersecurity technologies before others.
	TR5	I usually try out new cybersecurity technologies before other people do.
Observability (OB)	OB1	I have seen other people using AI-based cybersecurity tools.
	OB2	Others can easily observe the results of my use of AI-based cybersecurity tools.
	OB3	The results of using AI-based cybersecurity tools are clear and apparent to me.
	OB4	People can tell that I know more about AI-based cybersecurity tools since I started using them.
	OB5	Other cybersecurity professionals who use AI-based tools appear to enjoy using them.
User Trust (UT)	UT1	AI-based cybersecurity tools act in an honest and reliable manner when interacting with users.
	UT2	AI-based cybersecurity tools show care for my security needs and protection.
	UT3	AI-based cybersecurity tools provide knowledgeable and accurate assistance when detecting or handling threats.
	UT4	AI-based cybersecurity service providers respond promptly to issues related to the AI tool.
	UT5	AI-based cybersecurity tools are trustworthy and provide real security benefits to users.
Intention to Use	IU1	I intend to use AI-based cybersecurity tools.
	IU2	If I have access to AI-based cybersecurity tools, I would subscribe to AI-driven security services from trusted providers.
	IU3	Eventually, using AI-based cybersecurity tools will be easier than using traditional cybersecurity methods.
	IU4	I have the necessary training to use AI-based cybersecurity tools effectively.
	IU5	Given the increasing availability of AI-based cybersecurity technologies, I predict that I will intend to use them.